

Hydrokinetic Energy Applications within Hydropower Tailrace Channels: Implications, Site Optimization, and U.S. Potential

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Abstract

This project explores the feasibility of deploying hydrokinetic turbines within tailrace channels downstream of hydropower dams as an opportunity to increase energy production at existing plants or add generation capabilities at Non-Powered Dams (NPDs). Tailraces are unique and attractive locations for hydrokinetic energy harvesting as they offer several advantages: fast-moving currents and thus higher hydrokinetic potential, scheduled and quantifiable flow releases, proximity to existing structural and electrical infrastructures, and a low risk of new environmental impacts. However, energy-extracting turbines create flow resistance, inducing a small but measurable water level increase upstream of their location (in subcritical flows). Depending on the distance to the upstream dam, this backwater effect may diminish the available hydraulic head and reduce hydropower generation, defeating the initial value proposition.

Figure 1: Schematic of a tailrace hydrokinetic application and the momentum balance approach.

This study proposes a simple 1D momentum balance approach to estimate the water level increase as a function of tailrace hydraulics (Froude number), turbine operating conditions (power coefficient), and the relative obstruction of the turbine within the channel cross-section (blockage ratio). The model is based on non-dimensional relationships, and thus it is agnostic of turbine and channel-specific geometries. Preliminary water level estimations are validated against three previous laboratory and field measurements at different scales. By combining the traditional backwater equation for open channel flows with the water level increase model, the optimal turbine siting distance can be determined to maximize net power production (balancing hydropower loss vs. hydrokinetic gain) while remaining within the tailrace boundaries to capitalize on its pre-existing benefits.

Finally, using a subset of sites from the U.S. hydropower fleet with flow information downstream of the dam, we provide a high-level estimation of the hydrokinetic potential available in tailraces in the United States and discuss two case studies. Besides adding generation to existing dams, tailraces could also become viable sites for large-scale field testing of hydrokinetic devices. Developers and researchers could use these sites to install turbines within a highly engineered channel with well-defined boundary conditions and existing grid interconnection access, while also generating tangible revenue to help offset testing costs.